

**CHANGE MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES OF SCHOOL HEADS
ON LEADERSHIP TRANSITION AND ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE:
THEIR EFFECTS ON ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT IN
PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS IN REGION XII**

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Change Management Strategies of School Heads on Leadership Transition and Organizational Climate: their Effects on Organizational Commitment in Public Elementary Schools in Region XII

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Abstract. This study investigated how change management strategies, organizational climate, and organizational commitment contribute to school performance, creating a positive work environment, and strengthening teachers' dedication to the school. It specifically examined the extent of change management strategies; level of organizational climate; level of organizational commitment; the difference in the perception of school heads and teachers on the change management strategies; the difference in the perception of school heads and teachers on the organizational climate; the relationship between the change management strategies and the organizational commitment of teachers, and the relationship between the organizational climate and the organizational commitment of teachers. This quantitative study examined change management strategies, organizational climate, and teachers' organizational commitment in public elementary schools in Region XII. Using descriptive and correlational research designs, teachers and school heads were selected according to predetermined inclusion criteria. The study included 315 randomly selected teachers and 24 school heads, using complete enumeration, and they responded to two adapted research questionnaires. Data were analyzed using mean, standard deviation, Independent Samples Mann-Whitney U Test, and Spearman's rho (ρ). The study found that school heads and teachers demonstrate a very extensive level of change management strategies. The organizational climate was rated very high by both school heads and teachers. Teachers demonstrate a very high level of organizational commitment, indicating strong leadership practices and a positive school environment that support teachers' dedication to their work and the school's goals. The findings revealed a significant difference in how school heads and teachers perceive change management strategies and organizational climate. The correlation analysis found no significant relationship between the change management strategies and teachers' organizational commitment. On the other hand, there is a significant relationship or weak positive correlation between the organizational climate and teachers' organizational commitment, suggesting that improvements in the school climate slightly increase teachers' commitment.

Keywords: Change Management Strategies; Organizational Climate; Organizational Commitment

Introduction

Every institution experiences change, and schools are no exception. Effective management of leadership transitions is essential for maintaining goals, supporting progress, motivating teachers, and ensuring stability, while poor management may reduce performance, create confusion, and lower morale. Key elements of effective change management include communication, sponsorship, stakeholder engagement, readiness, learning and development, measurement, and sustainability (ACMP, 2020), while distributed leadership strengthens collaboration and trust (Thien et al., 2022).

In the Philippines, DepEd Order No. 7, s. 1999 mandates regular reassignment of school heads, which can create transition challenges if not well managed. School climate strongly influences teacher motivation and performance, while organizational commitment is shaped by affective, continuance, and normative dimensions (Meyer & Allen, 1991), and is affected by leadership and climate conditions.

In Region XII, these factors are vital for readiness, dedication, and retention. Hence, this study examined the extent of change management strategies, the level of organizational climate, and the level of organizational commitment. It also sought to determine the differences in perceptions between school heads and teachers regarding change management strategies and organizational climate, as well as to analyze the relationships between change management strategies and teachers' organizational commitment, and between organizational climate and teachers' organizational commitment.

Research Questions

The study examined the relationship of change management strategies, organizational climate, and the teachers' organizational commitment in selected public elementary schools in Region XII.

Specifically, it addressed the following questions.

1. What is the extent of practice of change management strategies as perceived by the school heads and teachers in Region XII during leadership transition in terms of:
 - 1.1. Communication;
 - 1.2. Sponsorship;
 - 1.3. Stakeholder engagement;
 - 1.4. Change impact and readiness;
 - 1.5. Learning and development;
 - 1.6. Measurement and benefits realization; and,
 - 1.7. Sustainability?
2. What is the level of organizational climate as perceived by the school heads and teachers in public elementary schools in Region XII during leadership transition in terms of:
 - 2.1 Supportive behavior;
 - 2.2 Directive behavior;
 - 2.3 Restrictive behavior;
 - 2.4 Collegial behavior;
 - 2.5 Intimate behavior; and,
 - 2.6 Disengaged behavior?
3. What is the level of organizational commitment of teachers in public elementary schools in Region XII during leadership transition in terms of:
 - 3.1 Affective commitment;
 - 3.2 Continuance commitment; and,
 - 3.3 Normative commitment?
4. Is there a significant difference in the perception of school heads and teachers on the change management strategies?
5. Is there a significant difference in the perception of school heads and teachers on the organizational climate?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the change management strategies and the organizational commitment of teachers in Region XII?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the organizational climate and the organizational commitment of teachers in Region XII?

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study examined how school leaders use strategic change management during leadership transitions and its relationship with organizational climate and teachers' commitment in public elementary schools in Region XII, specifically in Koronadal City, General Santos City, Kidapawan City, and Tacurong City Divisions. It also explored how teachers and school leaders perceive these change management strategies, as well as their views on school climate and teachers' level of commitment.

Literature Review

Change Management Strategies

Change management is the structured process of implementing change by preparing people, setting strategies, and reducing resistance. It helps leaders determine what change is needed and how to implement it effectively. While goals remain the same, methods may be adjusted, and change can occur gradually or through major shifts, but both require proper planning and support. Effective change is important because it strengthens leadership and organizational performance, builds trust, and helps institutions achieve their goals (Shulga, 2021). Idogawa et al. (2023) further emphasize that organizations must be able to plan, control, and manage change to remain competitive and sustainable in a rapidly changing environment.

Organizational Climate

Research consistently shows that a positive school climate strongly influences teacher behavior, well-being, and retention. Sun et al. (2024) found that supportive environments enhance organizational citizenship, instructional effectiveness, and optimism, encouraging teachers to go beyond their basic duties. Wei et al. (2024) further explain that a positive school climate reduces stress and emotional strain, increasing job satisfaction and lowering teacher turnover. Janiukštis et al. (2024) add that communication, autonomy, and workplace support improve well-being and reduce harassment, strengthening both safety and performance. In addition, Wang (2024) emphasizes that in digital and blended learning settings, technology also shapes perceptions of school climate, highlighting the importance of both physical and virtual work environments.

Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment is a key concept in understanding employee attitudes, behavior, and performance, grounded in Meyer and Allen's (1991) Three-Component Model: affective, continuance, and normative commitment. Meyer et al. (2002) confirmed that these components are distinct and strong predictors of job satisfaction, performance, and turnover, making the model highly relevant in research and practice. Recent studies extend this framework across contexts, with Bai and Vahedian (2023) finding that affective and normative commitment reduce nomophobia in digital workplaces through organizational ethics, while Hessari et al. (2023) show that individual innovation helps buffer technostress, highlighting the importance of flexibility and creativity in sustaining engagement.

Methodology

Research Design

This research employed descriptive and correlational designs to examine change management strategies during leadership transitions, school organizational climate, and teachers' organizational commitment in Region XII. According to Singh (2024), descriptive research describes current conditions, trends, and behaviors without influencing them, focusing on what, where, when, and how. Meanwhile, as noted by Romana and Gestoso (2025), the correlational design was used to analyze relationships among change management strategies, organizational climate, and organizational commitment. A comparative component was also included to assess differences in the perceptions of school leaders and teachers regarding change management strategies and organizational climate.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Region XII. Region XII was selected as a key location where a leadership change can affect numerous schools, educators, and learners. Additionally, the region actively implements DepEd rules regarding school staffing, reassignment, and recruitment.

Research Participants

The respondents were public elementary school heads and teachers from four city divisions in Region XII. Schools were selected based on the following criteria: located in a city division, offering complete elementary education (Kindergarten to Grade 6), classified as mega schools with at least 50 teachers, and led by principals who had experienced at least three leadership transitions. Teacher respondents were permanent with at least five years of service and experience with leadership transitions. A total of 315 teachers were selected using stratified sampling with proportionate allocation, while 24 school heads were included through complete enumeration. Overall, 339 respondents participated in the study to ensure comprehensive insights.

Research Instrument

This study used two survey questionnaires to gather data from school heads and teachers. The first, a researcher-developed tool based on the Association of Change Management Professionals (2020), assessed change management strategies during leadership transitions using a 5-point Likert scale (1–Never to 5–Always). The second, adapted from Wayne K. Hoy's OCDQ-RE, measured organizational climate on a 5-point scale from very low to very high. Teachers' organizational commitment affective, continuance, and normative was assessed using the model of John P. Meyer and Natalie J. Allen (1991, 1997), also with a 5-point Likert scale. The instruments were validated by six experts and tested for reliability with 30 similar respondents outside the study sample.

Data Gathering Procedure

To obtain approval from the relevant authorities, the researcher first secured approval by submitting a request letter to the Regional Director of Region XII. After approval, permission was obtained from the Schools Division Superintendents and School Heads to conduct the study and administer surveys. Once all

approvals were granted, the researcher distributed the questionnaires with clear instructions and allowed sufficient time for completion. The surveys were then personally collected to ensure a high retrieval rate. After collection, the responses were reviewed, organized, and prepared for statistical analysis. All data were kept confidential and used solely for academic and research purposes.

Results and Discussions

Research Question 1: What is the extent of practice of change management strategies as perceived by the school heads and teachers in Region XII during leadership transition in terms of, Communication, Sponsorship, Stakeholder Engagement, Change Impact and Readiness, Learning and Development, Measurement and Benefits Realization and Sustainability?

Table 1. Extent of Practice of Change Management Strategies as Perceived by the School Heads and Teachers in Region XII in terms of Communication.

Statements	School Heads			Teachers		
	M	SD	Verbal Description	M	SD	Verbal Description
1. The SH provide a clear and specific details when communicating about the leadership transition.	4.79	0.41	Very Extensive	4.51	0.58	Very Extensive
2. The SH used communication methods that have worked well with teachers and staff in the past.	4.71	0.46	Very Extensive	4.60	0.59	Very Extensive
3. The SH follows a clear schedule and timing when giving updates about the transition.	4.71	0.46	Very Extensive	4.59	0.67	Very Extensive
4. The SH prepare how to communicate possible problems or crises related to the transition.	4.54	0.51	Very Extensive	4.47	0.69	Very Extensive
5. The SH make sure the communication reduced rumors, confusion, and misinformation.	4.58	0.50	Very Extensive	4.64	0.55	Very Extensive
Section Mean	4.67	0.22	Very Extensive	4.56	0.43	Very Extensive

Findings show that both school heads and teachers perceived communication as a very extensive change management strategy during leadership transitions. School heads rated it very extensive ($M = 4.67$, $SD = 0.22$), indicating strong emphasis on clear and effective communication, consistent with Faupel and Helpap (2021). Teachers also rated it highly extensive ($M = 4.56$, $SD = 0.43$), suggesting that communication efforts effectively reduced rumors and misinformation, aligning with Yue and Walden (2021). Overall, the results highlight that clear, transparent communication supported smoother transitions, strengthened trust and cooperation, and fostered readiness for change, supporting the view of Ophilia and Hidayat (2022) that leaders play a key role as communicators.

Table 2. Extent of Practice of Change Management Strategies as Perceived by the School Heads and Teachers in Region XII in terms of Sponsorship.

Statements	School Heads			Teachers		
	M	SD	Verbal Description	M	SD	Verbal Description
1. The SH regularly received guidance from sponsors to help keep the transition on track.	4.88	0.34	Very Extensive	4.50	0.61	Very Extensive
2. The SH clearly understood the purpose of the transition because it was well-explained by the sponsors	4.79	0.41	Very Extensive	4.41	0.78	Very Extensive
3. The SH had the necessary resources and budget for the transition as provided or approved by the sponsors.	4.75	0.61	Very Extensive	4.34	0.84	Very Extensive
4. The SH was able to address problems and obstacles during the change with support from the sponsors.	4.00	0.78	Extensive	4.27	0.89	Very Extensive
5. The SH recognized that the sponsors' role was important to the success of the transition	4.71	0.46	Very Extensive	4.58	0.57	Very Extensive
Section Mean	4.63	0.25	Very Extensive	4.42	0.54	Very Extensive

Findings show that both school heads and teachers perceived sponsorship as a very extensive change management strategy during leadership transitions. School heads rated it very extensive ($M = 4.63$, $SD = 0.20$), indicating strong support, guidance, and resource provision from sponsors, consistent with Breese et al. (2020). Teachers also rated it very extensive ($M = 4.42$, $SD = 0.54$), reflecting recognition of sponsors' involvement, though slightly lower due to less direct interaction, aligning with Albrecht et al. (2022). Overall, the results highlight that visible and active sponsorship plays a crucial role in ensuring successful transitions by providing direction and stability.

Table 3. Extent of Practice of Change Management Strategies as Perceived by the School Heads and Teachers in Region XII in terms of Stakeholder Engagement.

Statements	School Heads			Teachers		
	M	SD	Verbal Description	M	SD	Verbal Description
1. The SH involves the stakeholders in decision-making before, during and after the transition.	4.75	0.44	Very Extensive	4.67	0.59	Very Extensive
2. The SH helps parents and the community understand why the transition is taking place.	4.71	0.46	Very Extensive	4.70	0.57	Very Extensive
3. The SH encourage feedback from teachers and staff during transition.	4.75	0.44	Very Extensive	4.63	0.60	Very Extensive
4. The SH communicates regularly with internal and external stakeholders about the transition.	4.54	0.51	Very Extensive	4.62	0.58	Very Extensive
5. The SH involves the stakeholder to help reduce resistance to the change.	4.58	0.50	Very Extensive	4.63	0.58	Very Extensive
Section Mean	4.67	0.28	Very Extensive	4.65	0.42	Very Extensive

Findings show that both school heads and teachers perceived stakeholder engagement as a very extensive change management strategy during leadership transitions. School heads rated it very extensive (M = 4.67, SD = 0.28), highlighting strong efforts in involving stakeholders throughout the process, consistent with Hollibaugh et al. (2019). Teachers also rated it very extensive (M = 4.65, SD = 0.42), recognizing its importance in communication, participation, and building community support, aligning with Adhi and Muslim (2023) and Saka-Helmhout et al. (2024). Overall, the results emphasize that stakeholder engagement strengthens collaboration, trust, and acceptance of change, supporting Bernat et al. (2023).

Table 4. Extent of Practice of Change Management Strategies as Perceived by the School Heads and Teachers in Region XII in terms of Change Impact Readiness.

Statements	School Heads			Teachers		
	M	SD	Verbal Description	M	SD	Verbal Description
1. The SH explained how the transition would affect teachers' work.	4.88	0.34	Very Extensive	4.61	0.54	Very Extensive
2. The SH creates contingency plans to ensure smooth operations during the transition.	4.63	0.49	Very Extensive	4.58	0.61	Very Extensive
3. The SH make sure the resources were available to support the changes.	4.58	0.50	Very Extensive	4.51	0.63	Very Extensive
4. The SH discusses the challenges of the transition with teachers	4.33	0.48	Very Extensive	4.45	0.69	Very Extensive
5. The SH believe the school was ready for the transition.	4.88	0.34	Very Extensive	4.51	0.71	Very Extensive
Section Mean	4.66	0.20	Very Extensive	4.53	0.43	Very Extensive

Findings show that both school heads and teachers perceived change impact readiness as a very extensive change management strategy during leadership transitions. School heads rated it very extensive (M = 4.66, SD = 0.20), indicating strong preparedness and proactive efforts in addressing structural and relational aspects of change, consistent with Treuer et al. (2018). Teachers also rated it very extensive (M = 4.53, SD = 0.43), reflecting general agreement on readiness efforts, though with slight concerns, aligning with Weiner (2020). Overall, the results highlight that clear communication about the impact of transition strengthens readiness, shared understanding, and trust.

Table 5. Extent of Practice of Change Management Strategies as Perceived by the School Heads and Teachers in Region XII in terms of Learning and Development

Statements	School Heads			Teachers		
	M	SD	Verbal Description	M	SD	Verbal Description
1. The SH arrange training sessions for teachers during the transition.	4.79	0.41	Very Extensive	4.16	0.99	Extensive
2. The SH guides teachers in adjusting to new roles and expectations.	4.75	0.61	Very Extensive	4.50	0.71	Very Extensive
3. The SH encouraged peer support and mentoring during the transition.	4.88	0.34	Very Extensive	4.44	0.75	Very Extensive
4. The SH promotes continuous learning as part of the change process.	4.75	0.44	Very Extensive	4.45	0.74	Very Extensive
5. The SH recognized and celebrated teachers' efforts to grow professionally during the transition.	4.29	0.95	Very Extensive	4.45	0.72	Very Extensive
Section Mean	4.69	0.29	Very Extensive	4.40	0.48	Very Extensive

Findings show that both school heads and teachers perceived learning and development as a very extensive change management strategy during leadership transitions. School heads rated it very extensive (M

= 4.69, SD = 0.29), indicating strong support for teachers' growth through training, mentoring, and peer support, consistent with Prosci (2025). Teachers also rated it very extensive (M = 4.40, SD = 0.48), though slightly lower, reflecting recognition of support in adjusting to new roles, aligning with Albrecht et al. (2022). Overall, the results highlight that learning and development initiatives help strengthen readiness and adaptation during transitions. According to De Kok et al. (2023), recognition of teacher growth and training opportunities received lower ratings, suggesting the need to further enhance feedback and recognition.

Table 6. Extent of Practice of Change Management Strategies as Perceived by the School Heads and Teachers in Region XII in terms of Measurement and Benefits Realization

Statements	School Heads			Teachers		
	M	SD	Verbal Description	M	SD	Verbal Description
1. The SH monitors the progress of the transition.	4.88	0.34	Very Extensive	4.36	0.71	Very Extensive
2. The SH check whether the transition improved school performance.	4.96	0.20	Very Extensive	4.42	0.74	Very Extensive
3. The SH check whether the transition improved school performance.	4.46	0.88	Very Extensive	4.41	0.71	Very Extensive
4. The SH compares results before and after the transition.	4.88	0.34	Very Extensive	4.43	0.70	Very Extensive
5. The SH uses data to confirm if the transition was successful.	4.46	0.88	Very Extensive	4.46	0.70	Very Extensive
Section Mean	4.73	0.32	Very Extensive	4.41	0.50	Very Extensive

Findings show that both school heads and teachers perceived measurement and benefits realization as a very extensive change management strategy during leadership transitions. School heads rated it very extensive (M = 4.73, SD = 0.32), indicating strong confidence in tracking progress and ensuring that changes lead to meaningful improvements, consistent with Kerzner (2020). Teachers also rated it very extensive (M = 4.41, SD = 0.50), reflecting recognition of consistent evaluation of outcomes and alignment with Benassi et al. (2021). Overall, the results highlight strong implementation of outcome measurement and benefits realization in schools.

Table 7. Extent of Practice of Change Management Strategies as Perceived by the School Heads and Teachers in Region XII in terms of Sustainability

Statements	School Heads			Teachers		
	M	SD	Verbal Description	M	SD	Verbal Description
1. The SH works on sustaining the positive results of the transition.	4.47	0.68	Very Extensive	4.29	0.81	Very Extensive
2. The SH created plans to continue improvements after the transition.	4.51	0.69	Very Extensive	4.88	0.34	Very Extensive
3. The SH encourages teachers to maintain new practices.	4.58	0.63	Very Extensive	4.79	0.41	Very Extensive
4. The SH aligned transition results with long-term school goals.	4.58	0.62	Very Extensive	4.75	0.61	Very Extensive
5. The SH ensures that good practices were not lost over time.	4.61	0.60	Very Extensive	4.33	0.48	Very Extensive
Section Mean	4.55	0.45	Very Extensive	4.61	0.30	Very Extensive

Findings show that both school heads and teachers perceived sustainability as a very extensive change management strategy during leadership transitions. School heads rated it very extensive (M = 4.55, SD = 0.45), indicating strong efforts to maintain and preserve positive changes in schools, consistent with Millar et al. (2012). Teachers rated it slightly higher (M = 4.61, SD = 0.30), reflecting strong recognition of sustainability practices and alignment with Setyadi et al. (2025). Overall, the results show that schools actively sustain improvements after transitions through structured planning and leadership support. However, the lowest-rated areas, though still very extensive, suggest the need to further strengthen long-term monitoring and sustainability mechanisms, as emphasized by Sancak (2023)

Table 8. Extent of Practice of Change Management Strategies as Perceived by the School Heads and Teachers in Region XII

Statements	School Heads			Teachers		
	M	SD	Verbal Description	M	SD	Verbal Description
1. Communication	4.67	0.22	Very Extensive	4.56	0.43	Very Extensive
2. Sponsorship	4.63	0.25	Very Extensive	4.42	0.54	Very Extensive
3. Stakeholder Engagement,	4.67	0.28	Very Extensive	4.65	0.42	Very Extensive
4. Change Impact and Readiness	4.66	0.20	Very Extensive	4.53	0.43	Very Extensive
5. Learning and Development	4.69	0.29	Very Extensive	4.40	0.48	Very Extensive
6. Measurement and Benefits Realization	4.73	0.32	Very Extensive	4.41	0.50	Very Extensive
7. Sustainability	4.55	0.45	Very Extensive	4.61	0.30	Very Extensive
Grand Mean	4.66	0.15	Very Extensive	4.50	0.22	Very Extensive

The grand mean for school heads is 4.66 (SD = 0.15), indicating a Very Extensive practice of change management strategies, which suggests strong leadership in driving school engagement and success. This supports Ulit (2025), who emphasizes the key role of school leaders in implementing educational reforms and creating measurable change. For teachers, the grand mean is 4.50 (SD = 0.22), also indicating a Very Extensive perception of change management, reflecting high engagement and involvement in school transitions. This aligns with Sasson et al. (2022), who stress that stakeholder engagement builds shared vision and commitment to change through collaboration and support. Overall, the results show that change management is effectively practiced in schools, with strong leadership from school heads and active involvement of teachers.

Research Question 2: What is the level of organizational climate as perceived by the school heads and teachers in public elementary schools in Region XII during leadership transition in terms of Supportive behavior, Directive behavior, Restrictive behavior, Collegial behavior, Intimate behavior and, Disengaged behavior?

Table 9. Level of Organizational Climate as Perceived by School Heads and Teachers in Region XII during Leadership Transition in terms of Supportive Behavior

Statements	School Heads			Teachers		
	M	SD	Verbal Description	M	SD	Verbal Description
1. The SH goes out of their way to help teachers.	4.58	0.72	Very High	4.74	0.49	Very High
2. The SH listens to and accepts teachers' suggestions.	4.50	0.72	Very High	4.60	0.62	Very High
3. The SH looks out for the personal welfare of teachers.	4.88	0.34	Very High	4.71	0.52	Very High
4. The SH treats teachers as equals.	4.79	0.41	Very High	4.77	0.45	Very High
5. The SH compliments teachers.	4.75	0.61	Very High	4.81	0.39	Very High
Section Mean	4.70	0.21	Very High	4.72	0.43	Very High

Findings show that both school heads and teachers perceived supportive behavior as very high during leadership transitions. School heads rated it very high (M = 4.70, SD = 0.21), indicating strong supportive leadership practices that promote trust, collaboration, and motivation, consistent with Millar et al. (2012). Teachers also rated it very high (M = 4.72, SD = 0.43), reflecting a highly supportive environment where they feel valued and encouraged, aligning with Sancak (2023). Overall, the results highlight that supportive leadership strengthens a positive organizational climate during transitions.

Table 10. Level of Organizational Climate as Perceived by School Heads and Teachers in Region XII during Leadership Transition in terms of Directive Behavior

Statements	School Heads			Teachers		
	M	SD	Verbal Description	M	SD	Verbal Description
1. The SH gives specific instructions and sets expectations that teachers must follow.	4.58	0.72	Very High	4.79	0.41	Very High
2. The SH directs teachers by providing feedback aimed at improving their work.	4.46	0.88	Very High	4.77	0.47	Very High
3. The SH explains the reasons behind feedback to guide teachers' actions.	4.88	0.34	Very High	4.77	0.44	Very High
4. The SH guides teachers step by step to improve weaknesses.	4.79	0.41	Very High	4.67	0.49	Very High
5. The SH monitors classroom activities to ensure teachers follow set of instructions.	4.75	0.61	Very High	4.73	0.45	Very High
Section Mean	4.69	0.31	Very High	4.74	0.38	Very High

Findings show a high level of directive behavior during leadership transitions, with both school heads and teachers rating it as very high. School heads reported a section mean of (M = 4.69, SD = 0.31), indicating strong confidence in providing clear instructions, feedback, and close supervision, consistent with structured leadership practices. Teachers also rated it very high (M = 4.74, SD = 0.38), suggesting that they experience

clear guidance, expectations, and monitoring from school heads. Overall, the results show a close alignment in perceptions, with teachers rating directive behavior slightly higher than school heads. This suggests that while school heads view their directive practices as structured and purposeful, teachers experience these actions as even more pronounced in daily school operations. The findings imply the need to ensure that directive leadership remains balanced with support and autonomy so that guidance does not feel overly controlling while still maintaining clear direction and instructional effectiveness.

Table 11. Level of Organizational Climate as Perceived by School Heads and Teachers in Region XII during Leadership Transition in terms of Restrictive Behavior

Statements	School Heads			Teachers		
	M	SD	Verbal Description	M	SD	Verbal Description
1. The SH strictly monitors attendance every morning, allowing little flexibility.	3.23	1.41	Moderate	4.14	1.01	High
2. The SH rigidly organizes routine duties, leaving teachers limited autonomy.	2.83	0.96	Moderate	3.92	1.14	High
3. The SH tightly schedules teachers' work, restricting their flexibility in teaching.	2.29	0.81	Low	3.84	1.13	High
4. The SH controls the number of committee assignments, limiting teachers' choices.	3.25	0.74	Moderate	3.67	1.21	High
5. The SH organizes administrative tasks in a way that constrains teachers' ability to manage their own time.	3.29	0.62	Moderate	3.94	1.16	High
Section Mean	2.98	0.44	Moderate	3.90	1.00	High

Findings show a difference in perceptions of restrictive behavior during leadership transitions. School heads rated it as moderate ($M = 2.98$, $SD = 0.44$), suggesting that they view existing controls as necessary for order and efficiency without being overly restrictive, consistent with Rezky et al. (2024). In contrast, teachers rated it as high ($M = 3.90$, $SD = 1.00$), indicating that they experience stronger control and limitations in their work, aligning with Hossny (2023). Overall, the results reveal a gap in perception, with school heads underestimating the level of restriction felt by teachers. This suggests the need to balance administrative control with teacher autonomy and strengthen open communication and participation in decision-making to improve the organizational climate.

Table 12. Level of Organizational Climate as Perceived by School Heads and Teachers in Region XII during Leadership Transition in terms of Collegial Behavior

Statements	School Heads			Teachers		
	M	SD	Verbal Description	M	SD	Verbal Description
1. The SH observes that teachers accomplish work with enthusiasm and commitment.	4.54	0.51	Very High	4.65	0.48	Very High
2. The SH notices that teachers accept the faults of their colleagues.	4.17	0.48	High	4.51	0.58	Very High
3. The SH sees that teachers provide help and support to each other.	4.54	0.72	Very High	4.66	0.43	Very High
4. The SH recognizes that teachers show pride in their school.	4.67	0.48	Very High	4.73	0.45	Very High
5. The SH ensures that new teachers are welcomed by their colleagues.	4.75	0.44	Very High	4.74	0.46	Very High
Section Mean	4.53	0.42	Very High	4.66	0.41	Very High

Findings show that both school heads and teachers perceived collegial behavior as very high during leadership transitions. School heads rated it very high ($M = 4.53$, $SD = 0.42$), indicating strong professional relationships, cooperation, and mutual support in the school environment, consistent with Alzahmi et al. (2022). Teachers rated it slightly higher ($M = 4.66$, $SD = 0.41$), reflecting a highly collaborative and supportive workplace that strengthens morale and belonging, also aligned with Alzahmi et al. (2022). Overall, the results highlight a strong collegial climate that supports stability and teamwork during transitions.

Table 13. Level of Organizational Climate as Perceived by School Heads and Teachers in Region XII during Leadership Transition in terms of Intimate Behavior

Statements	School Heads			Teachers		
	M	SD	Verbal Description	M	SD	Verbal Description
1. The SH observes that teachers consider other faculty members at this school as their closest friends.	4.67	0.48	Very High	4.47	0.68	Very High
2. The SH notices that teachers invite colleagues to visit at home	4.46	0.51	Very High	4.62	0.60	Very High
3. The SH is aware that teachers know the family background of their colleagues	4.42	0.50	Very High	4.50	0.93	Very High
4. The SH sees that the teachers enjoy socializing during free time	4.50	0.72	Very High	4.45	0.72	Very High
5. The SH recognizes that teachers hold parties for one another	4.50	0.72	Very High	4.38	0.92	Very High
Section Mean	4.51	0.28	Very High	4.48	0.38	Very High

Findings show that both school heads and teachers perceived intimate behavior as very high during leadership transitions. School heads rated it very high ($M = 4.51$, $SD = 0.28$), indicating strong interpersonal relationships, mutual support, and positive social interaction among teachers, consistent with Von Bergen (2020). Teachers also rated it very high ($M = 4.48$, $SD = 0.38$), reflecting a supportive work environment that strengthens trust, teamwork, and morale, aligned with Jung et al. (2021). Overall, the results highlight strong interpersonal relationships that support collaboration and stability during transitions.

Table 14. Level of Organizational Climate as Perceived by School Heads and Teachers in Region XII during Leadership Transition in terms of Disengaged Behavior

Statements	School Heads			Teachers		
	M	SD	Verbal Description	M	SD	Verbal Description
1. The SH observes that faculty meetings are unproductive and do not contribute to school improvement.	2.01	0.82	Low	1.88	0.68	Very Low
2. The SH notices that teachers leave school immediately after classes and neglect school-related tasks.	2.12	0.91	Low	2.38	0.77	Low
3. The SH sees that teachers refuse to work cooperatively with the majority.	2.13	0.64	Low	2.04	0.81	Low
4. The SH recognizes that teachers do not support colleagues who follow school policies.	2.20	0.75	Low	2.04	0.62	Low
5. The SH observes that teachers communicate unclearly and lose focus during faculty meetings.	1.95	0.73	Low	2.00	0.83	Low
Section Mean	2.08	0.48	Low	2.07	0.53	Low

Findings show that both school heads and teachers perceived disengaged behavior as low during leadership transitions. School heads rated it low ($M = 2.08$, $SD = 0.48$), indicating that teachers remain committed, cooperative, and actively involved in school activities, suggesting a stable and supportive school environment in Region XII. Similarly, teachers rated it low ($M = 2.07$, $SD = 0.53$), reflecting continued engagement, responsibility, and participation in school tasks despite leadership changes, consistent with Morrissey et al. (2020). Overall, the results indicate that disengagement is not a major concern in schools during transitions.

Table 15. Level of Organizational Climate as Perceived by the School Heads and Teachers in Region XII

Statements	School Heads			Teachers		
	M	SD	Verbal Description	M	SD	Verbal Description
1. Supportive Behavior	4.70	0.21	Very High	4.72	0.43	Very High
2. Directive Behavior	4.69	0.31	Very High	4.74	0.38	Very High
3. Restrictive Behavior	2.98	0.44	Moderate	3.90	1.00	Very High
4. Collegial Behavior	4.53	0.42	Very High	4.66	0.41	Very High
5. Intimate Behavior	4.51	0.28	Very High	4.48	0.38	Very High
6. Disengaged Behavior	2.08	0.48	Low	2.07	0.53	Low
Grand Mean	4.22	0.16	Very High	4.41	0.28	Very High

Among the six indicators, school heads rated Supportive Behavior highest ($M = 4.70$, $SD = 0.21$), showing strong support for teachers and students, consistent with Ulit (2025). Directive Behavior also rated high ($M = 4.69$, $SD = 0.31$), indicating clear guidance in implementing reforms. Collegial ($M = 4.53$, $SD = 0.42$) and Intimate Behavior ($M = 4.51$, $SD = 0.28$) reflect strong collaboration and relationships, while Disengaged Behavior was lowest ($M = 2.08$, $SD = 0.48$), showing active engagement. Restrictive Behavior

was relatively lower ($M = 2.98$, $SD = 0.44$), suggesting limited control practices and a need for more collaborative approaches, as noted by Ahmed et al. (2024). For teachers, the grand mean ($M = 4.41$) indicates a very high organizational climate. They also rated Supportive ($M = 4.72$, $SD = 0.43$) and Directive Behavior ($M = 4.74$, $SD = 0.38$) very high, consistent with Sasson et al. (2022), showing strong leadership support and guidance. Collegial ($M = 4.66$, $SD = 0.41$) and Intimate Behavior ($M = 4.48$, $SD = 0.38$) reflect strong collaboration and trust. However, Restrictive Behavior ($M = 3.90$, $SD = 1.00$) suggests some perceived limitations, while Disengaged Behavior remains low ($M = 2.07$, $SD = 0.53$), indicating active involvement. Overall, both groups perceive a very high organizational climate marked by strong support, collaboration, and engagement.

Research Question 3: What is the level of organizational commitment of teachers in public elementary schools in Region XII during leadership transition in terms of Affective commitment, Continuance commitment and, Normative commitment?

Table 16. Level of Organizational Commitment of Teachers in Region XII in terms of Affective Commitment

Statements	M	SD	Verbal Description
1. As a teacher, I demonstrate a strong sense of belonging to the school.	4.81	0.41	Very High
2. As a teacher, I enjoy working with colleagues and school leadership.	4.86	0.37	Very High
3. As a teacher, I take pride in being part of the school.	4.87	0.35	Very High
4. As a teacher, I show emotional attachment to the school's mission and values.	4.80	0.45	Very High
5. As a teacher, I feel unhappy if required to leave the school.	4.38	0.85	Very High
6. As a teacher, I feel connected to the school's vision and goals.	4.74	0.46	Very High
7. As a teacher, I find teaching at the school personally fulfilling.	4.77	0.44	Very High
8. As a teacher, I am motivated to contribute to the success of the school	4.82	0.38	Very High
9. As a teacher, I show personal commitment to the school community.	4.75	0.43	Very High
10. As a teacher, I demonstrate loyalty to the school beyond professional obligations	4.79	0.43	Very High
Section Mean	4.76	0.34	Very High

Findings show that teachers exhibit a very high level of affective commitment ($M = 4.76$, $SD = 0.34$), indicating strong emotional attachment, pride, belonging, and motivation toward their school, consistent with Meyer and Allen (1991). This suggests that teachers in Region XII are highly connected to their school's mission and goals and are motivated to contribute to its success. Overall, teachers demonstrate strong emotional commitment; however, the relatively lower rating on willingness to leave indicates that practical factors such as job satisfaction, career opportunities, work-life balance, and external conditions may still influence retention. This implies that emotional attachment alone is not enough to ensure long-term retention. Schools should therefore address both emotional and practical needs by providing professional growth opportunities and improving working conditions to strengthen teacher loyalty and reduce turnover.

Table 17. Level of Organizational Commitment of Teachers in Region XII in terms of Continuance Commitment

Statements	M	SD	Verbal Description
1. As a teacher, I stay in this school because leaving would result in loss of benefits.	4.43	0.85	Very High
2. As a teacher, I remain because leaving the school could create financial difficulties.	4.37	0.88	Very High
3. As a teacher, I stay due to the challenge of finding a similar teaching position elsewhere.	4.30	0.90	Very High
4. As a teacher, I remain because of the time and effort already invested in this school.	4.46	0.81	Very High
5. As a teacher, I perceive that the costs of leaving outweigh the benefits of moving to another school.	4.46	0.78	Very High
6. As a teacher, I stay because other teaching opportunities are less secure than the current position.	4.44	0.74	Very High
7. As a teacher, I remain to maintain stability for self and family.	4.54	0.62	Very High
8. As a teacher, I stay to sustain the current lifestyle.	4.49	0.73	Very High
9. As a teacher, I rely on the school's support program for professional or personal needs.	4.49	0.68	Very High
10. As a teacher, I perceive that starting over in another school would be inconvenient or risky.	4.49	0.70	Very High
Section Mean	4.50	0.66	Very High

Findings show that teachers in Region XII exhibit a very high level of continuance commitment ($M = 4.50$, $SD = 0.66$), indicating a strong intention to remain in their schools due to the perceived costs and risks of leaving. This reflects a practical or calculative form of commitment, where teachers stay because of concerns such as loss of benefits, financial instability, and difficulty finding comparable employment, consistent with Meyer and Allen (1991). Julian et al. (2024) also note that continuance commitment is driven by awareness of the risks and costs of leaving rather than emotional attachment. Overall, teachers remain in

their schools mainly for stability and practical reasons, including job security and family considerations. However, the relatively lower concern about difficulty finding another job suggests that retention is influenced more by stability and personal circumstances than by job scarcity alone. This indicates that continuance commitment reflects a balance between practical security needs and overall work environment stability.

Table 18. Level of Organizational Commitment of Teachers in Region XII in terms of Normative Commitment

	Statements	M	SD	Verbal Description
1.	As a teacher, I feel a moral obligation to remain in the school.	4.56	0.58	Very High
2.	As a teacher, I stay because it is considered the right thing to do.	4.59	0.62	Very High
3.	As a teacher, I continue teaching to support students during leadership changes.	4.64	0.49	Very High
4.	As a teacher, I feel responsible for the school's continuity and success.	4.66	0.53	Very High
5.	As a teacher, I believe that leaving the school would let down colleagues or students.	4.43	0.75	Very High
6.	As a teacher, I feel a sense of loyalty that requires remaining in the school.	4.60	0.65	Very High
7.	As a teacher, I stay because the role as a teacher entails commitment to the school.	4.64	0.53	Very High
8.	As a teacher, I feel a duty to help the school succeed under new leadership.	4.64	0.55	Very High
9.	As a teacher, I remain because of an obligation to support the school community.	4.63	0.59	Very High
10.	As a teacher, I stay because teachers should remain committed through organizational changes.	4.74	0.48	Very High
	Section Mean	4.63	0.46	Very High

Findings show that teachers in Region XII exhibit a very high level of normative commitment ($M = 4.63$, $SD = 0.46$), indicating a strong moral obligation to remain in their schools. This reflects a sense of duty, loyalty, and responsibility to support the school's continuity and success, especially during periods of change. Meyer and Allen (1991) describe normative commitment as staying in an organization because of a perceived obligation rather than emotional or practical reasons. Overall, teachers remain in their schools due to a strong sense of responsibility to the organization and its values. However, the relatively lower concern about letting down colleagues or students suggests that this obligation is more general toward the school rather than strongly tied to personal impact on others. This indicates that normative commitment is primarily driven by moral responsibility and loyalty to the institution.

Table 19. Level of Organizational Commitment of Teachers in Region XII

	Dimensions	M	SD	Verbal Description
1.	Affective Commitment	4.76	0.34	Very High
2.	Continuance Commitment	4.50	0.66	Very High
3.	Normative Commitment	4.63	0.46	Very High
	Grand Mean	4.61	0.41	Very High

The grand mean of 4.61 ($SD = 0.41$) shows that teachers in Region XII have a very high level of organizational commitment across affective, continuance, and normative dimensions. This indicates that teachers are emotionally attached to their schools, feel a moral obligation to stay, and also recognize practical reasons for remaining. High organizational commitment is linked to better job performance, satisfaction, and retention (Hidayat et al., 2022; Toala-Mendoza et al., 2025). Affective commitment is the highest ($M = 4.76$, $SD = 0.34$), showing strong emotional attachment and alignment with school goals, which supports greater motivation and engagement (Li et al., 2022). Normative commitment ($M = 4.63$, $SD = 0.46$) reflects a strong sense of duty and responsibility that promotes collaboration and organizational citizenship behaviors (Kalitanyi, 2022). Continuance commitment is the lowest ($M = 4.50$, $SD = 0.66$) but still very high, indicating retention is also influenced by practical factors like job security and benefits, though it contributes less to motivation and innovation (Mujajati et al., 2022; Nguyen et al., 2023). Overall, teachers in Region XII show strong commitment driven mainly by emotional attachment and moral responsibility, with practical considerations also supporting retention. To sustain and improve this, school leaders should strengthen affective and normative commitment through supportive leadership, shared values, and continuous professional development.

Research Question 4: Is there a significant difference in the perception of school heads and teachers on the change management strategies?

Table 20. Result of Mann-Whitney U Test on Change Management Strategies as Perceived by School Heads and Teachers

Respondents	<i>n</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>U</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>r_{rb}</i>
Teachers	315	4.50	0.223	2057	<.001	0.447
School Heads	24	4.66	0.154			

Note: $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance

The Mann-Whitney U test shows a significant difference between school heads and teachers in their perception of change management strategies during leadership transitions ($U = 2057, p < .001$), indicating that the two groups view the process differently. School heads reported higher perceptions ($M = 4.66, SD = 0.154$) than teachers ($M = 4.50, SD = 0.223$), with a moderate effect size ($r_{rb} = 0.447$), suggesting a meaningful difference. This implies that school heads, being directly involved in planning and implementation, tend to view change management more positively, while teachers, as recipients of change, may feel less involved or informed, shaping their more cautious perception. The result highlights the importance of involvement and communication in shaping perceptions of change. Overall, the finding suggests that improving teacher participation, communication, and feedback mechanisms can enhance understanding and acceptance of change. This is supported by Kotter's Change Model (1996), Bass's Transformational Leadership Theory (1990), and Litwin and Stringer's Organizational Climate Theory (1968), which all emphasize communication, leadership support, and a positive climate in successful change implementation.

Research Question 5: Is there a significant difference in the perception of school heads and teachers on the organizational climate?

Table 21. Result of Mann-Whitney U Test on Organizational Climate as Perceived by School Heads and Teachers

Respondents	<i>n</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>U</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>r_{rb}</i>
School Heads	24	4.22	0.166	2106	<.001	0.428
Teachers	315	4.41	0.281			

Note: $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance

The Mann-Whitney U test shows a significant difference in perceptions of organizational climate between school heads and teachers ($U = 2106, p < .001$), indicating that the two groups view the school environment differently. Teachers rated the organizational climate more positively ($M = 4.41, SD = 0.281$) than school heads ($M = 4.22, SD = 0.166$), with a moderate effect size ($r_{rb} = 0.428$), showing a meaningful difference. This suggests that school heads and teachers experience the school climate based on their different roles. School heads, who manage operations and handle administrative responsibilities, may experience more pressure, leading to a less favorable view. In contrast, teachers, who focus more on classroom interaction and receive support in their work, tend to perceive the climate more positively. Overall, the findings show that organizational climate is experienced differently depending on roles and responsibilities. This highlights the need for stronger communication, collaboration, and participation in decision-making to improve shared understanding. The result is supported by Litwin and Stringer's Organizational Climate Theory (1968), Bass's Transformational Leadership Theory (1990), and Lewin's Change Theory (1951), which emphasize leadership, communication, and environmental conditions in shaping workplace perceptions.

Research Question 6: Is there a significant relationship between the change management strategies and the organizational commitment of teachers in Region XII?

Table 22. Testing of Significant Relationship on Change Management Strategies and Organizational Commitment among Teachers

		Change Management Strategies	Organizational Commitment
1. Change Management Strategies	Spearman's rho	---	---
	p-value	---	---
	Spearman's rho	-0.011	---
2. Organizational Commitment	df	313	---
	p-value	0.844	---

Note: $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance

The Spearman's rho analysis shows a very weak and non-significant negative relationship between change management strategies and teachers' organizational commitment ($\rho = -0.011, p = 0.844$), indicating no meaningful association between the two variables. Since the p-value is higher than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted, meaning change management strategies do not significantly influence teachers' commitment. This suggests that teachers' organizational commitment is shaped by other factors such as leadership behavior, school environment, emotional support, and job satisfaction rather than change management strategies alone. Even if change strategies are implemented, they may not strengthen

commitment if teachers do not feel valued, supported, or involved. Overall, the findings imply that school leaders should focus more on building strong relationships, improving communication, and fostering a supportive school culture. Strengthening transformational leadership practices and involving teachers in decision-making may be more effective in enhancing commitment than relying on change strategies alone. This is supported by Bass's Transformational Leadership Theory (1990) and organizational commitment theories, which emphasize emotional connection and supportive leadership as key drivers of commitment.

Research Question 7: Is there a significant relationship between the organizational climate and the organizational commitment of teachers in Region XII?

Table 23. Testing of Significant Relationship on Organizational Climate and Commitment among Teachers

			Organizational Climate	Organizational Commitment
1.	Organizational Climate	Spearman's rho	---	
		p-value	---	
2.	Organizational Commitment	Spearman's rho	0.305	---
		df	313	---
		p-value	<.001	---

Note: $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance

The results show a weak but significant positive relationship between organizational climate and organizational commitment ($\rho = 0.305, p < .001$), indicating that as the school climate improves, teachers' commitment slightly increases. Since the p-value is below 0.05, the relationship is statistically significant, so the null hypothesis is rejected; however, the weak correlation suggests the relationship is limited in strength. This means that while a positive school environment contributes to higher teacher commitment, it is not the only influencing factor. Other factors such as leadership support, workload, salary, and professional development opportunities also play important roles in shaping commitment. Overall, the findings suggest that improving organizational climate can help enhance teacher commitment, but it should be supported by strong leadership practices and better working conditions. This is consistent with Meyer and Allen's (1991) Three-Component Model and Bass's Transformational Leadership Theory (1990), which emphasize that both workplace environment and leadership support influence organizational commitment.

Ethical Considerations

This study followed ethical guidelines in conducting research with school heads and teachers in selected divisions of Region XII. Approval was obtained from the DepEd Regional Director and Schools Division Offices, and informed consent was secured, ensuring voluntary participation with no administrative consequences and use of data for academic purposes only. Confidentiality was maintained through coding and removal of identifying details, with results reported in aggregate to prevent identification. The study posed minimal risk, and anonymity was ensured, with no impact on employment, evaluation, or promotion. Participants' autonomy was respected, including their right to withdraw at any time. Fair selection was ensured through clear inclusion criteria and balanced representation across divisions. The researcher maintained scientific integrity by using validated tools, conducting accurate analysis, and reporting results truthfully. All data were securely stored, password-protected, and properly disposed of after the retention period, and data collection was scheduled to avoid disrupting school duties.

Conclusion

This study examined the perceptions of school heads and teachers on change management strategies, organizational climate, and teachers' organizational commitment in Region XII. Findings show that change management strategies were very extensively implemented, but school heads rated them more positively than teachers. Organizational climate was very high for both groups, and teachers' organizational commitment was also very high across affective, normative, and continuance dimensions. Significant differences were found in perceptions of both change management strategies and organizational climate. Results also show no significant relationship between change management strategies and commitment, while organizational climate has a weak but significant positive relationship with commitment. Overall, change management strategies do not directly influence teacher commitment, but organizational climate has a modest effect, and future research may use mixed methods for deeper analysis.

Recommendations

Change management strategies were perceived as very extensive, but teachers rated them lower than school heads, indicating the need to strengthen teacher involvement, transparent communication, and participatory decision-making to reduce perception gaps. School heads should sustain supportive, collegial, and engaging practices by strengthening relationships, shared responsibility, and open communication to maintain a positive climate and engagement. The Department of Education may enhance teachers' organizational commitment through continuous professional support, recognition, and career development

opportunities. School leaders may also promote collaborative transition processes, regular feedback, and climate assessments to improve alignment and responsiveness. In addition, strengthening trust, collegiality, and professional support can improve stability, while future studies may explore other influencing factors and use mixed methods for deeper understanding.

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